

Influence of organic matter on the adsorption of boron in two leached acidic soils of Indian sub-tropics

Mitali Mandal and Dilip Kumar Das*

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Mohanpur-741 252, Nadia, West Bengal, India

E-mail : mitali_mandal@rediffmail.com, dkdas1231@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 13 December 2011, revised 10 December 2012, accepted 07 January 2013

Abstract : The adsorption study of boron was conducted in two soils (inceptisol and alfisol) of Indian sub-tropics with the addition of graded doses of boron amended with and without organic matter. The results reveal that the amount of boron adsorbed was recorded an increase with increasing concentration of applied boron as well as equilibrium concentration of boron (B) in soils of alfisol and inceptisol treated with organic matter, but the percentage adsorption decreased with an increasing equilibrium concentration of B. The ratio of concentration in equilibrium to the amount adsorbed of B was recorded relatively higher in an alfisol compared to inceptisol. The magnitude of B adsorption without the application of organic matter was much less in both alfisol and inceptisol. The supply parameters of boron in soils of inceptisol and alfisol have been found to be increased with the application of boron, being increased a greater magnitude in an inceptisol when supplied with organic matter. The maximum buffering capacity of B in an inceptisol and alfisol treated with organic matter was recorded as 4.32 and 8.93, while that of the same without the application of organic matter was 35.23 and 6.21.

Keywords : Adsorption, boron, alfisol, inceptisol, organic matter.

Introduction

Adsorption-desorption processes play a major role in governing the solubility of B in soil solution and consequently its availability to growing plants. Boron is one of the seven essential micronutrients required for the normal growth of most plants. However, the range of B concentrations in the soil solution causing neither deficiency nor toxicity symptoms in plants is narrow. The amount of B adsorbed by soils varies greatly with the contents of various soil constituents, mostly clay minerals, sesquioxides and organic matter¹. Boron adsorption and desorption from adsorption sites of soil regulate the B concentration in the soil solution. This regulation depends on the changes in solution B concentration and on the affinity of the soil constituents for B². Thus, adsorbed B may buffer fluctuations in solution B concentration and B concentration in soil solutions may vary only slightly with changes in soil water content.

The role of organic matter in B distribution between the liquid and solid phases of soils is not yet fully under-

stood. Boron deficiency has been observed in soils with high organic matter content³⁻⁵. This deficiency has been shown to be related to the high affinity of organic matter to B⁵⁻⁸. Yermiyaho *et al.*⁸ observed that B adsorption capacity of composted organic matter was at least four times higher than that of clays and soils. This observation suggests that small amount of organic matter in soils may change significantly the B distribution between solid and liquid phases and thereby its availability to plants. In fact, organic matter is one of the main sources of B in acid soils as relatively little B adsorption occurs on the mineral fraction at low pH values⁹. It has been reported that B sorption by composted organic matter – soil mixture increased with an increasing rates of composted organic matter⁸. The incorporation of organic manures increased the reversibility of adsorbed B from soil¹⁰. Composted organic matter decreased B concentration in bell pepper plants and the effect was more prominent at high B rates¹¹. In India, about 33% soils are deficient in B and deficiency has been recorded in oilseeds, food

grains, vegetables and fruit crops¹². Application of FYM increased the retention of added B in soils and may help to reduce the leaching losses¹³.

The adsorption-desorption study showed that Fe_2O_3 and clay were primarily responsible for retaining added B, organic carbon, pH and cation exchange capacity positively influenced the adsorption of B while free Fe_2O_3 , organic carbon and clay retarded release of B from these soils. The degree of irreversibility (hysteresis) of B adsorption/desorption increased with an increase in organic carbon content and CEC of these soils.

Freundlich equation proved more effective in describing B adsorption in soils compared to Langmuir equation¹⁴. Organic carbon, cation exchange capacity and clay content positively influenced the adsorption of B, while cation exchange capacity and clay content retarded the release of B soils. The degree of irreversibility (hysteresis) of B adsorption/desorption increased with increase

in pH, organic carbon, cation exchange capacity and clay content of soil.

Adsorbed boron was significantly correlated with that of soil solution B concentration at equilibrium conforming its sorption to the Langmuir adsorption isotherm over a limited concentration range, while the Freundlich adsorption range (0.0 to 80 mg/ml) was an adequate for all the soils studied. Statistical analysis showed that clay content, acid extractable - B, $\text{CaCO}_3\%$ and cation exchange capacity (CEC) were significantly correlated with the Freundlich (k) value, while only organic matter and clay contents were significantly correlated with the Langmuir (b) value. Boron uptake by barley was linearly correlated with the boron content of soil solutions¹⁵.

Results and discussion

Adsorption of applied boron in soil with the addition of organic matter :

The results (Table 2) reveal that the amount of boron adsorbed has been found increased with an increasing concentration of applied boron as well as equilibrium concentration of B in soils of alfisol and inceptisol treated with organic matter, but the percentage adsorption decreased with increasing equilibrium concentration of B. However, the relative amount of boron adsorbed was higher in alfisol compared to inceptisol which might be explained by the greater amount of sesquioxides present in the soil as well as applied organic matter. The adsorption capacity of the composted manure was 3–13 times

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the experimental soil

Particulars	Alfisol	Inceptisol
Sand (%)	77.20	66.8
Silt (%)	8.00	22.2
Clay (%)	14.80	11.00
pH (1 : 2.5)	5.49	5.7
EC (1 : 2.5) dSm^{-1}	0.180	0.155
Organic carbon (%)	0.49	0.85
CEC [$\text{c mol (p}^+) \text{ kg}^{-1}$ soil]	9.10	12.10
Hot CaCl_2 -extractable B (mg kg^{-1})	0.134	0.146

Table 2. Adsorption of applied boron in two soils of West Bengal with the addition of organic matter

Soil	Applied boron (ppm)	Equilibrium concentration (C) (ppm)	Adsorbed B (ppm)	x/m ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	$C/x/m$	$\log C$	$\log x/m$
Inceptisol	0.5	0.16	0.34	0.68	0.266	-0.795	-0.221
	1	0.27	0.73	1.46	0.184	-0.568	0.164
	2	0.58	1.42	2.84	0.204	-0.236	0.453
	3	0.75	2.25	4.50	0.166	-0.125	0.653
	4	1.02	2.98	5.96	0.171	0.008	0.775
Alfisol	5	1.33	3.67	7.34	0.181	0.124	0.865
	0.5	0.10	0.40	0.80	0.125	-100	-0.096
	1	0.18	0.82	1.64	0.109	-0.740	0.214
	2	0.44	1.56	3.12	0.141	-0.350	0.404
	3	0.64	2.36	4.72	0.135	-0.193	0.673
	4	0.98	3.02	6.04	0.162	-0.008	0.781
	5	1.26	3.74	7.48	0.168	0.100	0.873

more than that of soils and incorporation of manures to the soils increased adsorption capacities which confirmed the results of present investigation¹⁰. However, the results of the present study are in conformity to that of results reported by⁸ who recorded increased B adsorption by composted organic matter-soil mixture to higher B adsorption capacity of the decomposition products of organic matter or microbial polysaccharides. The relatively lower amount of B adsorption in an inceptisol due to organic matter application might be ascribed to slightly higher pH resulting to much dominance of $B(OH)_4^-$ species causing less adsorption of B in organic matter applied soil being adsorption maxima -18.86 and 22.22 mg g^{-1} and constant related to bonding energy -0.229 and 0.402 ppm in soils of inceptisol and alfisol supplied with organic matter respectively (Table 3). The results suggest that inceptisol treated with organic matter exhibited very little adsorption of B compared to alfisol. Chemical bonding between B and organic molecules particularly carbohydrate and humic substances present in the applied organic matter may be responsible for boron adsorption⁷. The adsorption maxima (b) and constant related to bonding energy (k) were varied with soils.

Table 3. Langmuir adsorption isotherms for boron in soils applied with and without organic matter

Soils	With organic matter		Without organic matter	
	(b)	(k)	(b)	(k)
	Adsorption maxima ($\mu g\ g^{-1}$)	Constant related to bonding energy (ppm)	Adsorption maxima ($\mu g\ g^{-1}$)	Constant related to bonding energy (ppm)
Inceptisol	-18.86	-0.229	-4.23	-8.33
Alfisol	22.22	0.402	41.66	0.149

The results (Fig. 1) show that the amount adsorption of B in both the soils were followed a similar trend to that of the same soils without the application of organic matter. However, the magnitude of B adsorption was greater in an alfisol compared to inceptisol. The application of organic matter to inceptisol might have no positive effect on the adsorption of B which possibly due to the formation strong linkages with polyvalent metals in forming clay-organic matter complexes preventing adsorption of B¹⁷.

Fig. 1. Relationship between equilibrium concentration (C) and adsorbed amount of boron (x/m) in organic matter treated soils.

The results (Fig. 2) show that the ratio of equilibrium B concentration to the amount adsorbed in an inceptisol consistently decreased with the equilibrium B concentration in soil solution, while the ratio of the same in an alfisol slightly increased with the equilibrium B concentration in the soil solution when organic matter was not applied which might be due to higher values of adsorption maxima (b) and constant related to bonding energy in the alfisol as evidenced from the present study.

Fig. 2. Relationship between C and $C/x/m$ for adsorption of boron in soils without addition of organic matter.

The results (Fig. 3) show that the amount of B adsorbed in both soils of inceptisol and alfisol was linearly increased the equilibrium concentration of B in the soil solution when both soils were not treated with organic matter. However, the magnitude of such linear increase varied with soil properties affecting adsorption maxima and bonding energy, being greater in alfisol as the soil

Fig. 3. Relationship between equilibrium concentration (C) and adsorbed amount of boron (x/m) without organic matter treated soils.

was exhibited a much greater adsorption maximum in absence of organic matter.

The results (Fig. 4) reveal that the ratio of concentration in equilibrium to amount adsorbed of B was recorded relatively higher in an alfisol, being consistent increase with increasing concentration of B in equilibrium solution which might be due to its adsorption onto specific adsorption sites soil colloids caused by organic matter application, while the ratio of the same in inceptisol decreased with increasing concentration of B in equilibrium solution which might be due to relatively less adsorption of B in soils caused by less availability of specific sites for B adsorption.

Fig. 4. Relationship between C and $C/x/m$ for adsorption of boron in soils with addition of organic matter.

Adsorption of applied boron in soil without the addition of organic matter :

The results (Table 4) show that the amount of B adsorbed exhibited a similar trend of changes in both the soils without the application of organic matter. However, the magnitude of B adsorption without the application of organic matter was much less in both alfisol and inceptisol, being adsorbed at a higher rate in an alfisol where oxides of iron and aluminium content was high. Such decrease in adsorption due to non treating the soil with organic matter might be attributed to the fact that organic matter might be existed as clay-metal organic matter complexes where clay and organic matter are combined by strong linkages with polyvalent metals. The oxidation of native organic matter relates clay and polyvalent metals which

Table 4. Adsorption of applied boron in two soils of West Bengal without the addition of organic matter

Soil	Applied boron (ppm)	Equilibrium concentration (C) (ppm)	Adsorbed B (ppm)	x/m ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	$C/x/m$	$\log C$	$\log x/m$
Inceptisol	0.5	0.26	0.24	0.48	0.542	-0.585	-0.319
	1	0.40	0.60	1.20	0.333	-0.398	0.079
	2	0.74	1.26	2.52	0.294	-0.130	0.401
	3	0.92	2.08	4.16	0.221	-0.036	0.619
	4	1.21	2.79	5.58	0.217	0.083	0.747
Alfisol	0.5	0.1	0.40	0.80	0.125	-1.000	-0.096
	1	0.28	0.72	1.44	0.194	-0.552	-0.158
	2	0.62	1.38	2.76	0.224	-0.207	0.440
	3	0.72	2.28	4.56	0.157	-0.142	0.658
	4	1.12	2.88	5.76	0.194	-0.049	0.760
	5	1.38	3.62	7.64	0.180	-0.139	0.883

may form hydroxides immediately and such released inorganic colloids participate in B adsorption. The results suggest that small amount of organic matter in soils may change significantly the B adsorption between solid and liquid phases and thereby its availability to plants. The soils of the present study was acidic in reaction and in fact in such soils, organic matter is one of the main sources of B as little occurs on the mineral fraction at low pH values (pH < 5.0)⁹. Organic matter has little effect on B adsorption by a soil containing 1.21% organic matter², while adsorption capacity of B in an acidic soil increased after removal of organic matter¹⁷. Comparing the two soils, it was observed that the amount of B adsorbed with varying concentration of applied B was recorded a higher values in an alfisol compared to inceptisol without the application of organic matter which might be due to highest value of adsorption maxima (*b*) 41.66 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ in alfisol. The adsorption maxima (*b*) and constant related to bonding energy (*k*) in soils of inceptisol and alfisol without application of organic matter were recorded as -4.23 and 41.66 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and -8.33 and 0.149 ppm respectively (Table 3) suggesting an acidic reaction of inceptisol has no specific sites for B adsorption while the alfisol having acidic in reaction has specific sites and strong affinity for B adsorption which has also been reflected for the adsorption of B in soils.

Freundlich adsorption isotherm for B in soils :

The results for the changes in Freundlich adsorption isotherm in an alfisol and inceptisol with and without addition of organic matter are presented in Table 5, Figs. 5 and 6.

Among two soils there was a considerable variation in B adsorption capacity (*k*) and order of adsorption (*n*) values which was obviously due to the variation of their properties. The highest values of *n* (1.162) and *k* (6.378) was recorded in alfisol when it was not supplied with organic matter, whereas in inceptisol the highest values of *n* and *k* were recorded as 0.859 and 5.715 respectively.

Table 5. Freundlich adsorption isotherms for boron in soils applied with and without organic matter

Soils	Without organic matter		With organic matter	
	(<i>n</i>)	(<i>k</i>)	(<i>n</i>)	(<i>k</i>)
Inceptisol	0.859	5.175	0.650	4.219
Alfisol	1.162	6.378	0.939	6.095

Fig. 5. Relationship between log *C* and log *x/m* for adsorption of boron with addition of organic matter.

Fig. 6. Relationship between log *C* and log *x/m* for adsorption of boron without addition of organic matter.

tively. In both the soils, *n* and *k* values were recorded lower when these soils were treated with organic matter. Such decreased values of *n* and *k* with the addition of organic matter might be attributed to greater competition for the adsorption of B on adsorption sites of soils. Keren and Bringham¹ also reported similarly which confirmed the results of the present study. However, the decrease in values of *n* in both soils treated with organic matter might be due to provide of additional B adsorption sites of lower bonding energy suggesting very little loss of B due to leaching in acid soils of the present study. The present investigation also finds support with the results reported by¹³ who showed that the increase in B adsorption due to organic matter application to the alfisol having low initial

organic matter content.

Supply parameter of boron in soils :

The results (Table 6) show that the supply parameters of boron in soils of inceptisol and alfisol have been found to be increased with the application of boron, being increased a greater magnitude in an inceptisol when supplied with organic matter. The magnitude of such increase, however, varied with types of soils and organic matter application. The relatively higher supply param-

Table 6. Changes in supply parameter (SP) of applied B with and without application of organic matter in soils

Concentration (ppm) of B applied	With organic matter		Without organic matter	
	Inceptisol	Alfisol	Inceptisol	Alfisol
0.5	0.229	0.164	0.145	0.179
1	0.436	0.314	0.284	0.402
2	0.891	0.677	0.560	0.828
3	1.28	1.00	0.802	1.15
4	1.71	1.41	1.06	1.61
5	2.17	1.77	1.31	2.06

eters recorded in an inceptisol due to the low value of adsorption maxima and bonding energy compare to alfisol. On the contrary, the supply parameters of boron in an alfisol without the supply of organic matter was recorded a higher value compare to inceptisol, being greater magnitude of supply parameter recorded with the higher boron concentration.

The higher supply parameter of B in an alfisol without addition of organic matter might be due to the highest value of adsorption maxima resulting from the greater amount of Fe Al oxide present in the soil. The results further revealed that the highest supply parameter of boron (2.17) was recorded in an inceptisol when 5 ppm B was applied when it is supplied with organic matter whereas the same value was recorded highest (2.06) in an alfisol without the application of organic matter which might be due to the contribution of organic matter favourably in case of inceptisol resulting from little specific sites for B adsorption and adversely in case of alfisol resulting from the higher availability of the specific sites in the later soil. The results show that an increase in B adsorption in soils after removal of organic matter which was similar to that of results reported by Sarkar and Das¹⁷.

Maximum buffering capacity in soils treated with and without organic matter :

The results (Table 7) reveal that the maximum buffering capacity in inceptisol and alfisol treated with organic matter was recorded as 4.32 and 8.93, while that of the same without the application of organic matter was 35.23 and 6.21. In an inceptisol, the highest maximum buffer-

Table 7. Maximum buffering capacity of boron in soils treated with and without organic matter

With organic matter		Without organic matter	
Inceptisol	Alfisol	Inceptisol	Alfisol
4.32	8.93	35.23	6.21

ing capacity was 35.23 when it was not supplied with organic matter which suggests that the release of boron or conversely the adsorption of boron does not depend so much on organic matter rather much dependent on clay content while the adsorption of B in an alfisol may be dependent on organic matter as evidenced from the maximum buffering capacity value (8.93). The lowest value of maximum buffering capacity (4.32) with added organic matter in an inceptisol suggested that soil does not act as a strong buffer with respect to B supply capacity compared to alfisol recorded relatively greater value (8.93). The highest maximum buffering capacity (35.23) was recorded in inceptisol when it is not supplied with organic matter which suggested that the soil itself has a strong buffer with respect to B supplying capacity.

Experimental

Two types of soil viz. alfisol and inceptisol were selected for laboratory experiment. Alfisols and inceptisols were collected from the farmer's field (0–15 cm depth) of Jhargram (acidic reaction) in the district of Midnapore (W) and Mathabhanga in the district of Coochbehar, West Bengal respectively. The soil samples were then air dried, ground and passed through 80 mesh sieve. These samples were stored into properly marked polyethylene packets, appropriately sealed and stored in the laboratory. The initial physicochemical properties of these two soil are given in Table 1.

Soils without and treated with 1% well rotten farm yard manure (soil weight basis) were used for the study. A stock solution of 100 mg B L⁻¹ was prepared by dis-

solving requisite quantity of boric acid in B free distilled water. Five gram of air dried soil was taken in polypropylene tubes in duplicate and equilibrated with 25 ml of 0.01 M CaCl₂ solution containing 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mg B L⁻¹ for 24 h at room temperature (25 °C) after shaking for 2 h on a horizontal shaker. After equilibration, the content were centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant were decanted in plastic vials until analysed for B by Azomethine-H method¹⁶. The quantity of B adsorbed by soil was calculated as the difference between the initially added B level and the B concentration remaining in the supernatant after subtracting the concentration of native soil B presents in solution (0 mg B L⁻¹) from the latter.

All adsorbed data for B were fitted into Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption equations and determined various adsorption parameters as follows.

Freundlich adsorption equation :

$$\log x/m = 1/n \log C + \log K$$

where *C* is the equilibrium concentration in ppm, *K* and *n* are empirical constants which depend on the nature of adsorbent, adsorbate and temperature. A plot of $\log x/m$ vs $\log C$ gives a straight line with slope of $1/n$ and an intercept of $\log K$.

Langmuir adsorption equation :

$$C/x/m = 1/kb + C/b$$

where *C* is the equilibrium concentration in ppm, *x/m* is the amount adsorbed per unit mass of the material, *b* is the adsorption maxima and *k* is a constant related to bonding energy. A plot of $C/x/m$ vs *C* gave a straight line of slope $1/b$ and intercept $1/kb$ where from the Langmuir constants *k* and *b* values were calculated.

Supply parameter of boron :

The availability of boron in soils is governed by the mutual interaction of quantity (*q*), intensity (*c*) and kinetic parameters as regulated by the adsorption, desorption, chelation and diffusion of boron from soils to the plant roots.

Supply parameter :

$$SP = qc^{1/2}/k_1k_2^{1/4}$$

where *q* is the quantity, *c* is the intensity, and *k*₁ (*b*) and *k*₂ (*k*) are constants.

Maximum buffering capacity :

It was calculated by multiplying adsorption maxima (*b*) and constant (*k*) related to bonding energy derived from the Langmuir adsorption isotherm.

Conclusion

From the present study, it may be concluded that the adsorption of boron in both alfisol and inceptisol of Indian sub-tropics has been found to be influenced by the application of organic matter. Maximum buffering capacity and supply parameter of boron have also been affected by the application of organic matter by moderating the adsorption maxima and bonding energy of both soils. The results further suggested that the application of organic matter in an inceptisol does not have any influence on the adsorption of boron whereas the same adsorption in an alfisol is affected by the application of organic matter suggesting the importance of soil properties in the adsorption and desorption mechanism of B.

References

1. R. Keren and F. T. Bingham, *Adv. Soil Sci.*, 1985, 1, 229.
2. U. Mezemann and R. Keren, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1981, 45, 722.
3. N. V. Hu, N. Hirunburana and R. Z. Fox, *Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal.*, 1988, 19, 517.
4. H. A. A. Mascarenhas, M. A. C. D. Miranda, O. C. Bataglia, J. C. V. N. A. Pereira and R. T. Tanaka, *Bragntia*, 1988, 47, 325.
5. Z. Liu, Q. Zhu and L. Tang, *Acta Pedologica Sinica*, 1989, 26, 353.
6. K. C. Berger and P. F. Pratt, in : M. H. Nevekar, G. L. Bridger and L. B. Nelson (eds.), "Fertilizer Technology and Usage", Soil Sci. Soc. Am., Mdison, Wisconsin, 1963, p. 287.
7. U. Yermiyaho, R. Keren and Y. Chen, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1988, 52, 1309.
8. U. Yermiyaho, R. Keren and Y. Chen, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1995, 59, 405.
9. E. Okazaki and T. T. Chao, *Soil Sci.*, 1968, 255.
10. N. Zerrari, D. Moustani and M. Verloo, *Agrochimica*, 2001, 45, 206.
11. U. Yermiyaho, R. Keren and Y. Chen, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 2001, 65, 1436.
12. M. V. Singh, "Micro and Secondary Nutrients and Pollutants Research in India", Indian Institute of Soil Science, Bhopal, 2000, 1.

13. K. R. Sharma, P. C. Srivastava, P. Srivastava and V. P. Singh, *Chemosphere*, 2006, **65**, 769.
14. D. R. Chaudhary and L. N. Shukla, *Agrochimica*, 2004, **48**, 141.
15. N. S. Murtadha, I. T. Lazim and M. J. Raihan, *Journal of Agriculture and Water Resources Research, Soil and Water Resources*, 1988, **7**, 61.
16. B. Wolf, *Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal.*, 1971, **2**, 363.
17. J. Sarkar and B. Das, *Environ. Ecol.*, 1990, **8**, 280.